

Base Adducts of Bis (Salicylaldehydato) Copper (II) and Zinc (II)

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SEVERAL base adducts of beta-diketones of zinc (II) and copper (II) have been reported¹⁻⁴ earlier. The complexes of *o*-hydroxy aryl carbonyl compounds closely resemble those of beta-diketones. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the base adduct formation with salicylaldehydato complexes.

Metal chelates were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with salicylaldehyde in (1:2) ratio followed by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The precipitated compounds were washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*. Bis-(salicylaldehydato) zinc (II) was suspended in ethanol, base was added in (1:2) ratio and the mixture refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. Cu(II) chelate was refluxed with the base as the solvent. On keeping the clear solutions overnight crystalline compounds separated out.

Metal in the compounds was estimated by standard methods, Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using "Toshniwal's conductivity bridge". Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 Spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in *M*/100 (chloroform base mixture) solution with Unicam SP-500 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurement were made on solid specimens using Gouy method.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present investigation are of the composition $[ML_2 B_2]$ where 'M' is Cu (II) or Zn, (II), LH-Salicylaldehyde and 'B' is the nitrogen base. Zinc complexes are white crystalline solids whereas copper (II) complexes are blue or green needleshaped crystals. The compounds have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium the Λ_M values are very low (1-4 mhos) suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of copper (II) complexes, show them to be paramagnetic (1.8-1.9 B.M.). Most of the ligand absorption bands are shifted. $\nu(M-O)$ could not be recorded as it was beyond the range of instrument. $\nu(C=O)$ of salicylaldehyde is found to be in the range of 1620-1640 cm^{-1} in the base adducts. The characteristic band due to conjugated $C=O$ group of salicylaldehyde is observed at about 1660 cm^{-1} which shifts to lower frequency in the metal chelates (1605 cm^{-1}) and again slightly shifts to higher frequency in base adducts. Hence, all the complexes reported in the present investigation are six coordinated.

Copper (II) complexes in chloroformbase mixture show one broad absorption band in the 675-700 nm region ($\epsilon=80-100$). It has been observed^{5,6} that greenish colours and absorptions in the vicinity of 700 nm are indicative of penta- or hexa-coordinated Cu(II). Recent studies⁷ on electronic spectra of Cu (II) indicate that the three transitions :

$2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_1 (\gamma_1)$, $2B_1 \rightarrow 2B_2 (\gamma_2)$, $2B_1 \rightarrow 2E (\gamma_3)$ are close in energy and often give rise to a single broad band envelope. So the present complexes probably have a distorted octahedral configuration. This is in conformity with some earlier observations⁸ by Graddon *et al.*

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF CU(II) AND ZN(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C.)	Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%Metal Found Calcd.	
$[Zn(Sal)_2(I.Q)_2]$	204	2.0	—	12.61	12.98
$[Zn(Sal)_2(Q)_2]$	215	3.5	—	12.72	12.98
$[Zn(Sal)_2(\text{beta-Picoline})_2]$	171	2.4	—	12.82	13.19
$[Cu(Sal)_2(I.Q)_2]$	160	1.8	1.82	11.28	10.95
$[Cu(Sal)_2(Q)_2]$	217	1.5	1.88	11.28	10.89
$[Cu(Sal)_2(\text{beta-Picoline})_2]$	120*	1.2	1.85	12.92	12.64

* Denotes decomposition.

Sal=Salicylaldehyde, Q=Quinoline. I.Q.=Isoquinoline.

References

- B. K. MOHAPATRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO., *Z. anorg. allg. chem.*, 1970, **372**, 33.
- B.K. MOHAPATRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO., *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1970, **4**, 404.
- B. K. MOHAPATRA., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 3923.
- B. K. MOHAPATRA., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 3930.
- J. M. WATERS and T. N. WATERS., *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1964, 2489.
- J. M. WATERS and T. N. WATERS., *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1959, 1200.
- C. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORREL., *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1969, 897.
- D. P. GRADDON and G. M. MOCKLER., *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 617.

Physico-Chemical Studies on the Complex Formation of Zirconium and Thorium with some Organic Acid. Part II

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IN this communication a number of new complexes of zirconium and thorium with anthranilic acid and its halo derivatives are reported. The present study was carried out in order to see the effect of halo substitution on the chelation ability of HA.

Halo anthranilic acids were prepared by standard methods. Complexes were obtained by direct addition of potassium salt solution of the ligands to the metal solution in various molar ratios. The preparation method was same as described in a previous communication. Table 1 contains representative data of analysis of HA complexes. Analysis of the complexes of other acids revealed identical compositions.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF ANTHRANILIC ACID COMPLEXES

Molar ratio Metal : ligand	Complexes	% found			% Calculated		
		Metal	C	N	Metal	C	N
1 : 1	[Zr A (OH) ₂](OH)	32.91	31.61	5.05	32.73	30.22	5.04
1 : 2	[Th(A) ₂ (OH) ₂]	46.05	33.34	5.45	43.12	31.23	5.23
1 : 4	[Th(A) ₃](OH)	36.31	39.38	6.25	35.31	37.97	6.35

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT BANDS IN THE SPECTRA OF HA AND ITS COMPLEXES

Compound	ν (NH) ν (OH) (Cm ⁻¹)	&	ν (OH) bonded (Cm ⁻¹)	ν (CO) (Cm ⁻¹)	Ring vibration (Cm ⁻¹)	Antisymmetric carboxylate ion vibration (Cm ⁻¹)
HA	3480m		2598m	16770s	1615 s, 1580 s, 1521 s, 1610 s, 1570 s, 1505 m	1398 s
[Zr(A) (OH) ₂](OH)	3450m 3330m		—	—	1605 m, 1560 m, 1495 sh	1420 s
[Tr(A) ₂ (OH)] ₂	3418s, 3315s		—	—	1605 s, 1575 s, 1505 s	1425 s
[Th(A) ₃](OH)	3420m, 3320m		—	—		1430 s

The conductometric and potentiometric titrations at 27°C were carried out by the same methods and experimental set up as reported earlier¹. The complexes were isolated and their infrared spectra were examined with films on KBr plates in the range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ by perkin-Elmer I. R. 337 grating spectrophotometer and representative assignments of HA and its complexes are given in Table II.

Zirconyl ion seems to form the complexes of the general formula [Zr (OH)₂ (L)] OH, where HL is the ligand. Thorium forms 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes with all the acids, which was confirmed by direct conductivity and potentiometric titrations. The complex with molar ratio 1:1 could not be isolated, whereas, the complex with stoichiometric ratios 1:2 and 1:3 were isolated.

Infrared Spectra :

The bands occurring in the spectra of ligands and complexes in 3480-3355 cm⁻¹ region² are due to NH and OH stretching frequency. The negative shifts of 60 cm⁻¹ to cm⁻¹ in both NH stretching bands, suggest that amino group is involved in co-ordination.

The bands due to the hydroxyl group of COOH and the carbonyl group are absent in the complexes. Thus it appears that HA and its halo derivatives act as bidentate ligands, which is also supported by the work of Decker et. al. 3,4.

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References

1. C. S. PANDE and G. N. MISRA., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 292.
2. R. C. AGARWAL and R. P. SINGH., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2593.
3. J. S. DECKER and H. FRYE., *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1966, **B 21**, 522.
4. J. S. DECKER and H. FRYE., *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1966, **B 21**, 527.

Amperometric Titration of Lead with Phosphorus Pentasulphide & its Determination in Presence of Mercury and Silver

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ALTHOUGH few references are available for amperometric determination of lead,¹⁻⁵ there is no published data regarding the amperometric estimation of lead in presence of mercury and silver. In the present investigation, phosphorus pentasulphide has been used as an analytical reagent for the amperometric estimation of lead, which has also been determined in presence of mercury and silver. For the determination of lead, the method is based on the measurement of anodic current of the excess titrating agent after the end-point. For the estimation of the constituents of binary solutions, the method is based on the decrease in height of the reduction wave of the uncombined metal ion and increase in anodic current of excess titrant.

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